

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Modelling the VCF from the RSF Expander Kobol

Alvaro Crespo

Supervisor: Xavier Lizarraga

Co-Supervisor: Frederic Font

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my parents, for supporting me in every step of the journey to become the person I am today.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to all the people who supported me throughout this journey.

First of all, I want to thank my family for always being there through thick and thin, giving me their support even for my craziest ideas.

I also extend my thanks to all SMC fellow students I had the pleasure of meeting. You are all incredibly inspiring people in your own unique ways, and I'm confident you will find success no matter where your paths take you.

Thanks to my beloved Barcelona family. Thanks to Isa, The Acoustics, Tupper Team, Coalicion Navarroleonesa, Los Sinvergüenzas, and countless others. We might not share the same blood, but the amazing memories we share (and keep building every day) definitely make up for it. You gave me two of the best years of my life, and for that I can't wish for anything but the best for you all.

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Abstract

Since the mid 90s, developers have tried to recreate the sound of analog audio devices through digital devices. The biggest problem is to recreate the non-linearities that are so characteristic of analog circuits, and give those devices their specific sound.

Today, there are 3 main lines of work when it comes to analog circuit modelling. White box modelling tries to recreate an analog circuit by simulating real world components. Wave Digital Filters is an example of this. On the other hand, in black box modelling, the analog circuit is not considered, and neural networks are used to learn and replicate the behaviour of the circuit. Finally, grey box modelling, tries to take advantage of both worlds by combining techniques from white and black modelling.

This thesis presents a study on the modelling of the VCF from the Kobol RSF Expander, using black-box techniques. The RSF Kobol Expander is a synthesiser developed in 1979 by the french company RSF. Less than 1000 units were made, but its great sound led to it being used by Hans Zimmer or Depeche Mode amongst others. The VCF is a crucial module when it comes to subtractive synthesis, usually giving synthesisers their specific sound, and the filter in the Kobol is a 24dB low pass filter, with controls for cutoff frequency and resonance. Part of the study will be focused on creating a small dataset, that then will be used to train a state-of-the-art model.

Keywords: Synthesiser, Voltage-Controlled Filter, Black-box modeling, Virtual analog modeling

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Structure for the document

The document is structured with an introduction that provides the necessary background and foundational explanations, setting the stage for the research. The 'State of the Art' section focuses on the latest advancements and relevant recent literature. The methodology is described in detail, with justifications for the chosen methods. Results are presented clearly, followed by an analysis within the context of existing research. The document concludes with a discussion of limitations, and potential future research directions.

1.2 Motivation

In an effort to preserve and replicate the unique sound and characteristics of analog synthesizers, this project delves into creating a virtual model based on the VCF of the RSF Kobol Expander. Analog circuits often lack the precision of their digital equivalents. Components have different tolerances and are often affected by external factors such as temperature. Preserving these circuits is not a simple task, but by developing virtual circuits, we can emulate the imperfections and nuances of analog components, allowing us to recreate the warmth and character of the original hardware in a digital format. This approach ensures not only the longevity of

these classic sounds but also their accessibility to a wider audience, free from the limitations of physical components.

This project aims to extract a small dataset from the VCF of the synth that can be used to train a model.

1.3 Objectives

The main goal of this project is to go over the process of creating a virtual model of the VCF module from the RSF Kobil. This process involves all the steps, from gathering data from the synthesizer itself, to organizing the data into a small and comprehensive dataset, and using it to train a model.

1.4 Non linear systems

A nonlinear system is a mathematical or physical system whose behaviour cannot be described solely through linear relationships between inputs and outputs. They often involve phenomena such as feedback loops, amplification, saturation, and bifurcations, which can lead to unpredictable or chaotic behaviour. Examples of nonlinear systems are abundant across various fields, including physics, biology, economics, and engineering.

For instance, in physics, systems governed by nonlinear equations include chaotic dynamical systems like the Lorenz system or the double pendulum. In biology, the interactions between genes, proteins, and regulatory networks often exhibit nonlinear behaviour, leading to emergent properties and complex dynamics. In economics, models of supply and demand, as well as financial markets, frequently involve nonlinear relationships due to factors like feedback mechanisms and network effects.

Understanding nonlinear systems is crucial for predicting their behaviour, analysing stability, and designing control strategies. While they can be more challenging to analyse compared to linear systems, nonlinear systems also offer rich opportunities for exploring emergent phenomena and novel solutions to complex problems.

1.5 Synthesizers

A synthesizer is an electronic instrument that uses electricity to generate audio signals. They are based around the concept of voltage-controlled oscillators (VCOs) to generate audio waveforms, which are then processed through different modules to shape the output signals. The idea of synthesizers was pioneered by Bob Moog in 1964[1] with the introduction of the Moog synthesizer. However, there are other important landmarks, such as Buchla Electronic Musical Instruments (BEMI) in 1963[2], which diverged from the idea of the VCO, and Roland with the System 700 in 1976[3].

Even though there are several ways a synthesizer can generate sound today, early models relied on the concept of subtractive synthesis. This method works by generating a signal (VCO) and then shaping it by passing it through different modules. These modules apply various transformations to the signal, but the most common ones are filters, envelopes, and amplifiers. These modules are controlled via controlled voltage (CV), so it is common to see them under names such as “voltage-controlled filter” or simply their acronyms “VCF.” A “chain” of modules is usually referred to as a “patch,” and synthesizers can be manufactured in several configurations, ranging from closed patch synthesizers with built-in interfaces to semi-modular synthesizers with flexible patches to single modules that can be combined with other modules into limitless patch configurations.

1.5.1 Filters

Filters are one of the most basic tools to shape sounds, allowing you to cut or boost specific frequencies from a given signal. In the context of analog synthesizers, the most common filters are the Low-Pass Filter (LPF) and the High-Pass Filter (HPF).

Filters are arguably the most relevant part of a synthesizer because, even though oscillators create the waveforms, filters are usually attributed to the personality of the synthesizer, establishing a point of differentiation from one synth to another. A very famous filter is the “ladder” style filter, usually attributed to the sound of

Moog synthesizers. Other notable filters include state-variable filters, like the one in the Oberheim SEM, and the Korg35 filter used in the Korg MS-20, known for its self-oscillation capabilities, a feature shared with the Kobol Expander.

1.5.2 The RSF Kobol

RSF, or *Réalisation et Synthèse du Franche-Comté*, was a French synthesizer manufacturer that was active during the late 1970s and early 1980s. They are known for their synthesizers, like the Kobol and the Kobol Expander. The Expander extends the capabilities of the original Kobol by adding more sound-shaping options, including additional oscillators, filters, and modulation sources. It is known for its warm, rich analog sound and its ability to produce complex, evolving tones, making it a favorite among electronic musicians and collectors of vintage synthesizers. The RSF Kobol Expander's design and functionality reflect the innovative spirit of early electronic music technology. The Expander is a two-voice monophonic synthesizer with a semi-modular style architecture, featuring five main blocks described in order in the patch chain:

- The synthesizer has two Voltage-Controlled Oscillators (VCOs), each with its own Voltage-Controlled Amplifier (VCA). These VCOs operate at a standard 1 V/octave and offer a broad frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 100 kHz. VCO 2 can be synchronized relative to VCO 1, allowing for complex sound interactions. The available waveforms include triangle, ramp, doubled ramp, square, variable-width pulses, and pulses controlled by the ADS 2 envelope, with progressive mixing between these waveforms controlled by voltage. Additionally, there are tuning adjustments for both VCOs to ensure precise control over the generated tones.
- The VCF operates at 1 V/octave. This filter covers a frequency range from 5 Hz to 100 kHz and features a steep 24 dB/octave slope. It includes a resonance adjustment that can reach end-of-travel oscillation, adding versatility to the sound shaping. The VCF also offers keyboard control adjustment from 0

V/octave to 2 V/octave, allowing for dynamic tonal changes. Additionally, the amplitude can be adjusted using the ADS 2 control, providing precise modulation capabilities.

- The synthesizer features Attack, Decay, Sustain (ADS) envelope types, with the ADS1 envelope offering decay suppression. The time control range for the envelopes spans from 1 ms to 100 seconds, providing extensive flexibility for shaping the sound. The output amplitude ranges from 0 to 10 V. Additionally, the envelopes include a GATE input that can be triggered on either the rising or falling edge (by internal selection). The trigger threshold is set at 2 V, ensuring responsive and precise control over the envelope activation. ADS1 flows into the VCA which is placed as the last module before the output signal, and ADS2 is unpatched by default, allowing it to be used to control other parameters.
- The LFO has a frequency range spanning from 0.001 Hz to 100 Hz. This LFO provides both triangular and square signal outputs, offering versatile modulation options for shaping the synthesizer's sound.
- Additionally, the synth has a random digital noise generator (white or pink by internal selection), and a voltage processor that allows to add, multiply and invert any input signal

Figure 1: Image of the Kobol Expander

1.6 Virtual analog modelling

Virtual analog modelling is a technique used in audio signal processing to emulate the characteristics of analog hardware using digital algorithms. It aims to replicate the warmth, richness, and imperfections associated with traditional analog audio equipment, such as synthesizers, equalisers, and compressors, within a digital environment. Virtual analog models simulate the behaviour of analog circuits, including nonlinearities, saturation, and frequency response, to produce authentic sounds reminiscent of their hardware counterparts. This approach offers musicians, producers, and engineers the flexibility and convenience of digital audio workstations while retaining the sonic qualities and tactile feel of analog gear. Virtual analog modelling has become increasingly popular in music production, allowing for the creation of vintage-inspired sounds and effects with the convenience of modern technology.

1.6.1 Modelling techniques

In the realm of modelling and analysis, two fundamental methodologies stand out: white box modelling and black box modelling. These approaches serve as cornerstones in understanding complex systems and phenomena across diverse disciplines. White box modelling entails an in-depth exploration of the internal structures and mechanisms of a system, providing a comprehensive understanding of its functioning. Conversely, black box modelling focuses on the observable inputs and outputs of a system, abstracting away its internal complexities. Both methodologies offer unique perspectives and tools for analysis, prediction, and decision-making, contributing significantly to fields such as computer science, engineering, economics, and beyond. There is a third approach that combines aspects from both white box and black box modelling, and it is what is known as grey box modelling.

White box modelling

In virtual analog modelling, white box modelling involves a detailed examination of the internal structures and mechanisms of analog hardware components, such as filters, oscillators, and amplifiers. This approach seeks to understand the underlying

physics and electronics of analogue circuitry and replicate it using digital algorithms. By dissecting the circuitry and equations governing each component, white box modelling allows for precise emulation of the behaviour and characteristics of analog hardware. Engineers and researchers can design virtual analog models with a deep understanding of how each parameter and component contributes to the overall sound, enabling accurate replication and customisation.

Black box modelling

Black box modelling focuses on the overall input-output relationship of analog hardware without delving into the internal details. Instead of explicitly modelling the internal circuitry, black box modelling relies on empirical observations and measurements of the input-output behaviour of analog devices. This approach involves analysing the frequency response, harmonic distortion, and other characteristics of analog circuits and synthesising digital models that approximate these properties. While black box modelling may not offer the same level of insight into the underlying physics as white box modelling, it can be more efficient for capturing the overall sonic qualities of analog hardware and is often used in situations where detailed knowledge of the internal workings is not necessary.

This modelling technique is useful when the internal mechanisms of a system are complex, unknown, or not easily accessible. Instead of delving into the details of how the system operates, black box modelling focuses on analysing the relationships between inputs and outputs to infer patterns, correlations, or predictive models.

Grey box modelling

In grey box modelling, certain parameters or aspects of the internal circuitry may be known or inferred, allowing for more informed and nuanced modelling decisions. This partial transparency can come from a variety of sources, such as circuit schematics, datasheets, or empirical measurements of specific components. By incorporating this partial knowledge into the modelling process, grey box modelling can improve the accuracy and fidelity of virtual analog models while still maintaining some level

of efficiency and flexibility compared to white box modelling.

Grey box modelling can be particularly useful in situations where full transparency of the internal circuitry is not feasible or practical, but some understanding of the underlying physics is desired to achieve a more accurate emulation of analog hardware. By combining insights from both white box and black box modelling approaches, grey box modelling offers a versatile and effective method for creating high-quality virtual analog models that capture the essence of classic analog gear while leveraging the benefits of digital technology.

1.7 Neural Networks

Neural networks are computational models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain, designed to recognize patterns and relationships in data. They consist of layers of interconnected nodes, known as neurons, which process information by transmitting signals across weighted connections. The network is organized into three main types of layers:

- **Input Layer:** This layer receives the raw data inputs, such as images, text, or numerical values.
- **Hidden Layers:** These intermediate layers process the input data through a series of weighted connections and activation functions. The hidden layers extract and transform features from the input, enabling the network to learn complex patterns.
- **Output Layer:** The final layer produces the network's output, typically in the form of a prediction or classification.

Neural networks are trained by adjusting the weights of the connections based on the input data and feedback from the output. This training process allows the network to improve its accuracy and effectiveness in tasks such as image recognition, natural language processing, and time series forecasting.

1.7.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning model designed specifically for processing structured grid data such as images. They consist of multiple layers of convolutional filters, which learn to extract hierarchical features from input data through convolutional operations. CNNs are widely used in computer vision tasks such as image classification, object detection, and image segmentation, due to their ability to automatically learn relevant features directly from the raw pixel values of images.

1.7.2 Long Short-Term Memory Networks

Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture specifically designed to capture long-term dependencies and patterns in sequential data. Unlike traditional RNNs, LSTMs incorporate specialised memory cells and gating mechanisms that allow them to selectively remember or forget information over time. This enables LSTMs to effectively model and predict sequences of data with complex temporal dynamics, making them well-suited for tasks such as speech recognition, natural language processing, and time series prediction.

Chapter 2

State of the art

2.1 Synthesizers

As of 2024, synthesizers are more advanced and diverse than ever, blending analog warmth with digital precision.

Hybrid synthesizers combine analog circuits with digital control, allowing for rich complex soundscapes. Some examples are the Sequential Prophet-10¹ and Moog One². But fully analog synthesizers are still manufactured, such as the Arturia PolyBrute³.

Eurorack and semi modular systems, like the Moog Matriarch⁴ allow for custom sound creation.

In terms of connectivity, MIDI 2.0 and MPE allow for increased resolution, bi-directional communication, better integration between hardware and software, and more expressive performances, with individual notes modulating independently in real-time.

¹<https://sequential.com/product/prophet-10/>

²<https://www.moogmusic.com/products/moog-one>

³<https://www.arturia.com/products/hardware-synths/polybrute/overview>

⁴<https://www.moogmusic.com/products/matriarch>

For the digital world, software synths such as Serum⁵ or Pigments⁶ offer a new approach to synthesis with wavetable synthesis.

2.2 Virtual analog modelling

2.2.1 Modelling techniques

White box modelling

White box modeling continues to be a cornerstone in audio signal processing, particularly for high-fidelity simulations of musical instruments and audio equipment. The field benefits significantly from advancements in computational techniques and a deeper understanding of the physical and electronic properties of audio systems. As these models evolve, they offer expansive potential for creating realistic, interactive simulations and improving the design and analysis of audio devices.

In audio signal processing, white box modeling has been applied to analog audio effects simulation with high realism. Recent research[4, 5] delves into modeling analog effect pedals, capturing intricate details and nonlinear behaviors. These models help simulate real-world acoustic phenomena with remarkable accuracy, allowing for the exploration of sound production mechanisms in virtual environments.

The physical modeling of the MXR Phase 90 pedal, as explored by Felix Eichas et al.[6], demonstrates the strength of white-box modeling in capturing the nuances of analog phase-shifting effects. By modeling the operational amplifier's behavior and the phase-shifting network, the research creates a digital replica that maintains the warm, vintage sound of the original pedal .

The work by Jaromír Mačák[7] highlights the challenges and solutions in modeling time-varying analog delay lines. White-box modeling in this context ensures that the digital flanger accurately mirrors the distinctive sweeping effects characteristic of BBD-based analog circuits .

⁵<https://xferrecords.com/products/serum/>

⁶<https://www.arturia.com/products/software-instruments/pigments/overview>

Finally, in 2019, Alberto Bernardini and Augusto Sarti[8] the concept of inverse virtual analog modeling is introduced as a method to refine and optimize white-box models by inversely designing the digital system based on desired audio characteristics. This technique enhances the accuracy and efficiency of digital audio effects, ensuring that the models not only replicate the sound but also the dynamic response of their analog counterparts.

Black box modelling

The increasing complexity and nonlinearity of modern audio effects, particularly those with time-varying characteristics, have driven the exploration of deep learning as a powerful tool for black box modeling. This approach offers the potential to create highly accurate and efficient models that can operate in real time, making it an invaluable asset in audio processing applications.

The work presented by Marco A. et al.[9] investigates various deep learning architectures for black box modeling of a wide range of audio effects, including both linear and nonlinear, as well as time-varying and time-invariant effects. The paper compares convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and WaveNet-based architectures, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses in different modeling tasks. The findings emphasize the importance of selecting the appropriate architecture based on the specific characteristics of the audio effect being modeled, and the potential of deep learning to generalize across different types of audio effects, offering a versatile solution for virtual analog modeling.

Later, in 2022, Christian J. Steinmetz and Joshua D. Reiss[10] presented an efficient deep learning architecture designed to model analog dynamic range compressors in real-time. By leveraging Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) with large receptive fields and techniques like feature-wise linear modulation (FiLM), the authors achieve a balance between high accuracy and real-time processing capability. The model's effectiveness is demonstrated through its ability to emulate the LA-2A compressor, a well-known analog device, maintaining both the nuanced dynamics and the time-dependent characteristics of the original hardware.

Marco Comunità et al.[11] focused on using deep learning, specifically Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs), to model black box audio effects that vary over time. The authors introduce time-varying feature modulation to improve the ability of these models to capture the long-range dependencies in audio signals. By integrating this approach into TCNs, the paper demonstrates significant advancements in modeling complex audio effects, such as fuzz distortion, which are characterized by their nonlinear and time-dependent behaviors. The proposed model is shown to outperform traditional methods, offering a more accurate and efficient solution for replicating these challenging audio effects.

Finally, Christopher Mitcheltree et al.[12] explore the challenge of modeling audio effects driven by low-frequency oscillators (LFOs), such as phasers, flangers, and choruses. The authors propose a method for extracting modulation features from processed audio to better replicate the time-varying nature of these effects. By focusing on the underlying modulation signals, the model can accurately reproduce the dynamic changes in sound characteristics that these effects are known for, even when the LFO signal is not directly accessible. This approach significantly enhances the flexibility and accuracy of black box modeling for time-varying audio effects.

Grey box modelling

A promising approach that has gained attention is gray box modeling. This method blends the strengths of both white-box and black-box modeling. White-box models rely on detailed physical descriptions of the system, often requiring intricate circuit analysis, while black-box models focus on input-output behavior without concern for the underlying mechanisms. Grey box modeling integrates these approaches by using partial knowledge of the system's physical properties and supplementing it with empirical data to refine the model. This technique is particularly useful in situations where full physical modeling is impractical due to complexity, yet where purely data-driven models may lack fidelity.

Champ Darabundit et al.[13] present a detailed approach to digitally emulating the Shin-ei Uni-Vibe, a 1960s-era analog effects pedal renowned for its unique modu-

lation sounds. The authors propose a gray box modeling technique that combines physical measurements with circuit analysis to recreate the distinctive sound of the Uni-Vibe. The model captures the interaction between the incandescent lamp and light-dependent resistors (LDRs) that drive the phase-shifting effect. This approach not only preserves the sonic character of the original pedal but also enables real-time implementation suitable for modern digital platforms.

Alec Wright and Vesa Välimäk[14] explore the application of gray box neural networks in modeling phaser and flanger effects, which are common audio effects in music production. The authors leverage machine learning techniques to create models that can replicate the behavior of these effects with high accuracy. By training neural networks on a dataset of input-output signal pairs, the models learn to approximate the non-linearities and time-varying characteristics of phasers and flangers. The results demonstrate that neural models can achieve a level of fidelity that rivals traditional analog circuit emulations, offering a computationally efficient alternative for real-time audio processing.

In another paper[14], they extend the application of neural networks to a broader class of audio effects characterized by periodic modulation. The focus is on developing models that can capture the dynamic behavior of effects like tremolo, vibrato, and chorus, which modulate sound parameters over time. The proposed neural models are designed to handle the temporal dependencies and non-linearities inherent in these effects. The paper showcases how neural networks can generalize across different modulation types, providing a versatile tool for digital audio effect emulation.

Finally, in 2022, a paper by Joseph T. Colonel et al.[15] introduces a method for reverse engineering distortion effects using a differentiable waveshaper model. Distortion effects, often used in music production to add harmonic content and character to audio signals, are typically non-linear and challenging to model accurately. The proposed approach involves using differentiable functions to approximate the transfer characteristics of distortion circuits. This method allows for the efficient optimization of parameters to match the behavior of specific distortion effects, offering

a powerful tool for creating digital emulations of analog distortion pedals.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter describes the steps taken to generate the dataset, followed by a brief description of the models used and how they were modified to fit the needs of the project.

3.1 Dataset

Due to the lack of valid a dataset, creating one was required to develop the project. Two units of the RSF Kobol were available, but only one was used to generate the data. The dataset consists of two subsets: the first one, referred to as 'static', and the second one, as 'dynamic'.

3.1.1 Data creation for static VCF envelopes

Since the static subset was the first contact with the project and the process of building a dataset, a few attempts were needed before being able to capture the data. Here is a description of the most relevant attempts.

First attempt

At the beginning of the recording process, a Universal Audio Apollo Twin X¹ audio interface was loaned to record the dataset (see Figure 2). This opened an interesting approach because the interface has DC-coupled outputs, meaning CV could be sent directly from the computer to the synthesizer. A project was set up with Bitwig Studio², where a couple of "HW CV" output modules (see Figure 3) sent controlled voltage through outputs 5 and 6.

Figure 2: Apollo Twin X audio interface

Figure 3: Bitwig's "HW" module

Because it was believed that the interface could only output CV through outputs 5 and 6, an external signal generated from the computer was input through the "VCF

¹<https://www.uaudio.com/uad-plugins/apollo-twin-x.html>

²<https://www.bitwig.com/overview/>

Audio In" to avoid using the VCO from the synthesizer. This was done because manipulating the VCO manually rather than via CV was considered unreliable in terms of reproducibility.

A 2-second noise signal, plus 2-second sweeps with sine, triangle, and square signals, was chosen. These signals were generated with Serum³, and the patches used can be found in the repository⁴. For the CV outputs, the automation curves (see Figure 4) were divided into 20 even steps, translating to a step of 0.5 volts. This would result in 1600 signals, or just below 55 minutes of audio.

Figure 4: Cutoff and resonance tracks in Bitwig

The outputs from the interface (5 and 6) were then connected to the voltage-controlled inputs for the VCF cutoff and the resonance, respectively, and output 2 was used to send the audio signals to the synthesizer.

After a few tries, this method was discarded for two main reasons:

- The interface has a Thunderbolt port, and the laptop being used at that time did not support this technology. This required relying on colleagues' computers, which limited the time available for testing and recording.
- The interface began to exhibit unexpected behavior where outputs 5 and 6 would send the same signal, even if configured to send independent ones. This made it impossible to control two parameters at the same time (cutoff and resonance).

³<https://xferrecords.com/products/serum/>

⁴https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/Thesis_code

Second attempt

A Focusrite Scarlett 18i20⁵ audio interface (see Figure 5) was loaned by a colleague, and the studio had a Doepfer MCV24 MIDI to CV converter (see Figure 6), so a new system was developed to generate the data. To begin with, Bitwig Studio was replaced by Ableton Live⁶, as it was a more familiar environment. A project was then set up where MIDI notes (see Figure 7) would be sent via the Focusrite 18i20 output to the MCV24, and outputs 5 and 6 from the converter were connected to the cutoff frequency and resonance of the VCF. A trigger signal was also sent to the synthesizer via output 17. The same serum signals were generated in Live, but this time the steps were divided every 1.25V, resulting in 8 values per parameter, or 64 output signals per input. This was done for the same four signals used in the first experiment. However, after a more thorough review, sweeps were disregarded as they did not align with recent trends, so a decision was made to switch to short 2-second signals of randomly generated notes, using the same three original signals (sine, triangle, and square). The MIDI notes used are described in Table 1.

Figure 5: Scarlett 18i20 audio interface

Figure 6: Doepfer MCV24

After generating the audio files with this method, it was realized that the amplitude of the "VFC Audio In" was very low, making the signals very noisy in the output.

It is hard to determine if this is the intended way for the synth to operate or if the device is malfunctioning due to its low maintenance state. Given the poor quality

⁵<https://focusrite.com/products/scarlett-18i20>

⁶<https://www.ableton.com/en/live/>

Figure 7: Ableton Live's piano roll with the MIDI notes

MIDI note	MIDI value	Est.Voltage(V)
G8	127	10
D#7	111	8.74
B5	95	7.48
G4	79	6.22
D#3	63	4.96
B1	47	3.70
G0	31	2.44
D#-1	15	1.18

Table 1: Recorded MIDI notes

of the results, a decision was made to use the oscillator from the synth instead.

Third attempt

After discarding the "VCF Audio In" as input, it was then decided to use the internal VCO from the synthesizer. The oscillator was carefully tuned to specific notes and then recorded for the same number of MIDI steps, resulting in 64 signals for each specific note. The notes used for this task were B2, B3, B4 and B5.

File processing

For each note, the 64 steps were recorded in a single take, at a sample of 48k Hz, and then exported as a single file with the names of the notes (see Figure 8). Following this, the raw audio files were processed using several Python scripts. The Ableton

project and the Python scripts are published on GitHub⁷.

Figure 8: Export parameters for the static subset

First of all, the exported tracks were cut and named into single signals with `data_cutter.py`. The names of the files are created by taking the note from the raw file's name, then adding the values for the resonance and cutoff. For example, for a B3, with resonance value of 31 and a cutoff value of 111 the name will be:

B3_r031_c111.wav

Then another Python script (`feature_extractor.py`) extracts the features for all the single signal files and store them into the `audio_features.csv` CSV file.

⁷https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/Thesis_code

3.1.2 Data creation for dynamic VCF envelopes

With the knowledge acquired extracting data for the first part of the dataset, this second part was a very smooth process. The key feature of a VCF is its ability to be controlled via CV, allowing the filter to become dynamic. In the Kobol Expander, this is achieved through the ADS 2 envelope generator, which modulates the filter's behavior.

- **Attack:** During the attack phase, the envelope gradually increases the cutoff frequency of the VCF from its initial value to its peak level. The speed of this rise is determined by the attack time. A slower attack results in a smoother, slower rise in the filter's cutoff, while a fast attack causes a quick rise, making the sound brighter quickly.
- **Decay:** After reaching the peak level, the decay stage controls how quickly the cutoff frequency decreases to the sustain level. This phase makes the filter's cutoff frequency fall, which can make the sound darker or less bright after the initial peak.
- **Sustain:** The sustain level sets the cutoff frequency that is maintained as long as the note is held. Unlike the other stages, which are time-based, the sustain stage is level-based. The cutoff frequency stays at this level until the note is released or the second decay phase starts.

For this subset, the goal was to generate signals of the same size, so the decision was made not to use the sustain function, meaning that the synth would only produce sound as long as a MIDI note was being sent to it.

The idea here was to choose 3 different values for the attack and decay (see Figure 9), and then record samples in the same way as described in the first part of the data creation, with a few variations. 4 different waveforms were used for each note, and 4 notes were recorded (B2, B3, B4, B5). The values for cutoff and resonance were the same ones as before with a exception.

Figure 9: Attack and Decay values used

File processing

For each note, 2 tracks were created. The first one recorded the signal from the synthesizer's "AUDIO OUT" output ("wet" from now on), and the second one recorded the signal from the synthesizer's "VCO 1 OUT" output("dry" from now on). Each track recorded a total of 640 in a single take, at a sample of 48k Hz, and then split based on attack and decay values, and exported (see Figure 10) with a name based on the attack and decay values, and the type of signal. For example, the wet file for B4, attack and decay values of .1 will be named:

`B4_.1.1_Wet.wav`

After that, the raw audio files were processed with several Python scripts. The Ableton project and the Python scripts are published on GitHub⁸.

The processing started by separating the tracks into single files. To do this the file `data_cutter_dynamic.py` was used. The code returned a total of 2560 single sounds for each note.

The naming system used in the other subset doesn't really with 5 different variables, so a decision was made to simply assign numbers to files, and the create a .csv file

⁸https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/Thesis_code

Figure 10: Export parameters for the static subset

that links the file with all its details called `file info.csv`.

Then another Python script (`feature_extractor_dynamic.py`) extracts the features for all the single signal files and store them into the `audio_features_dynamic.csv` CSV file. This process was repeated for the wet and dry files.

3.2 Models

For the modelling part, two different models were used, with varying results. The first one is based on the `Modulation Extraction for LFO-driven Audio Effects` model presented by Christopher Mitcheltree et al.[12], and the second one is based on the `pedalnet` model developed by Teddy Koker[16].

3.2.1 Modulation Extraction for LFO-driven Audio Effects

For the first model, the source code from the `Modulation Extraction for LFO-driven Audio Effects` paper is being used⁹. The paper presents a framework for extracting low-frequency oscillator (LFO) signals from processed audio to model audio effects like phasers, flangers, and choruses. This method enables the training of neural networks to emulate these effects without needing access to the original LFO signal. The system accurately extracts various LFO signals, including quasi-periodic and distorted ones, facilitating the end-to-end modeling of unseen analog and digital LFO-driven audio effects.

The aim is to adapt the code to the dataset and train the model to learn the behavior of the VCF.

The code utilizes PyTorch Lightning, a lightweight PyTorch wrapper that provides a high-level interface for organizing and managing machine learning experiments. It abstracts away much of the boilerplate code involved in training models with PyTorch, allowing users to focus on the research and logic of their models rather than the technical details of implementation.

There are several models and options in the original paper, but for the requirements of this project, the `LSTMEffectModel` was selected. This model processes an input audio signal by combining it with a latent representation, feeding this combined input through an LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) layer to capture temporal dependencies, and then applying a fully connected layer to produce an output. The

⁹https://github.com/christhetree/mod_extraction/

output signal is added to the original input signal and passed through a tanh activation function to ensure the final output is in the range $[-1, 1]$. This model maintains and updates a hidden state across forward passes to retain information over time.

To train this model, the dynamic subset was used. This is because this model works with modulation signals, similar to what the synthesizer's envelope does to the VCO's signal.

In order to split the dataset into training and validation sets, the file `train_val_split.py` was used. This file allows the creation of 4 new folders: `train_dry`, `val_dry`, `train_wet`, and `val_wet`, with any amount of files from the original dataset, at any percentage of training and validation. This allows for the easy creation of different-sized subsets if needed.

The forked repository used for the thesis can be found on GitHub¹⁰.

Technical Challenges

During the initial stages of this research, the forked codebase failed to run as expected, presenting an unexpected obstacle. Although the specific issues were not immediately apparent, it was evident that the code required extensive troubleshooting to achieve proper functionality. Given the complexity of the code and my initial lack of expertise in this specific area, a significant amount of time was invested in systematically testing different components, adjusting configurations, and making necessary modifications based on observed behavior.

The issues with the code were ultimately resolved following a subsequent update by the original author, implemented in response to a request. This update, which involved a code push, successfully rectified the problem and enabled the continuation of this work.

¹⁰https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/mod_extraction

3.2.2 Pedalnet

For the second model, the source code from `pedalnet` is being used¹¹. This research explores the application of deep learning techniques to emulate analog guitar effects, in particular the Ibanez Tube Screamer. By utilizing a neural network model inspired by WaveNet[17], the study is based around the work of Alec Wright et al.[18], and demonstrates the potential of machine learning in accurately replicating the tonal characteristics of analog audio hardware. The methodology involves data collection from the physical pedal, model training, and output evaluation, with results indicating that the emulated sound closely matches the original, offering potential for real-time audio processing applications.

The original code had some outdated methods, so a new version was developed. In the forked GitHub repository, `model.py` is the original code, and the files `model2.py`, `model3.py` and `model4.py` are different versions based on the original one.

- `model2.py` introduces several structural and functional enhancements to the original, emphasizing improved hyperparameter management, data handling, and integration with PyTorch Lightning’s best practices. Hyperparameters are now explicitly passed and saved using PyTorch Lightning’s `save_hyperparameters()` utility, streamlining logging and restoration processes. Validation outputs are managed through the use of a dedicated list, allowing for the computation of average loss in the `on_validation_epoch_end` method, which is more explicit and aligns with PyTorch Lightning’s methodology. Furthermore, data loading has been made more secure with a context manager for file operations, and the logging of training and validation losses has been updated to use the `self.log` function, enhancing compatibility with PyTorch Lightning’s features.
- `model3.py` extends the functionality from `model2.py` by incorporating two additional performance metrics: mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean squared error (RMSE). These metrics are not only computed but also systematically logged during both training and validation steps, providing a

¹¹<https://github.com/teddykoker/pedalnet>

more comprehensive evaluation of the model’s performance. Additionally, `model13.py` enhances the granularity of metric aggregation at the end of each validation epoch by averaging and logging all three metrics—loss, MAE, and RMSE. `model12.py` only averages and logs the loss. Additionally, this version increases data loading efficiency by configuring the data loaders to use twice as many worker threads (8 instead of 4), which can expedite the training process. These second version of the code is designed for more thorough model assessment and potentially faster data processing.

- `model14.py` introduces additional parameters for the cutoff and resonance, which modulate the model’s behavior during the forward pass. This change allows for the use of the static subset and a more dynamic processing, with the `PedalNet` class adapted to load and utilize these extra parameters. This version uses the same evaluation metrics (loss, MAE, RMSE) as the other ones.

It is important to note that this model operates on audio with a sample rate of 44.1 kHz, as opposed to the 48 kHz sample rate used in the original dataset. To address this discrepancy, the file `downsampler.py` from the `custom_code` folder in the forked repository was employed to perform the necessary downsampling.

The forked repository used for the thesis can be found on GitHub¹².

¹²<https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/pedalnet>

Chapter 4

Results

The results chapter follows a similar format as the previous one. The document first delves into the generated dataset, and then describes the output from the modelling part.

4.1 Dataset

The final dataset contains audio signals extracted from the RSF Expander Kobol. The output from the synthesiser was recorded for four different octaves, in order to obtain a big range in terms of pitch. All the recordings are provided in RIFF WAVE format with 44100 Hz sample rate, and a bit depth of 16 Bit. The dataset is made of 7936 audio signals, each of them with 3 seconds of duration, which means a total of 6 hours, 36 minutes and 48 seconds in terms of time.

The generated dataset has two main subsets, named `Kobol_VCO_dynamic`, and `Kobol_VCO_static`.

4.1.1 Kobol_VCO_static

The first subset of the dataset is made of 256 audio files, divided into 4 groups of 64, according to the MIDI note the VCO is playing. The naming for each file is created by combining the note played by the VCO, the MIDI value for the resonance, and

the MIDI value for the cutoff frequency. This means that every file's name will look like this:

BX_rY_cY.wav

Where X ranges from 2 to 5, and Y can be 15, 31, 47, 63, 79, 95, 111 or 127.

Additionally, there is a CSV file called `audio_features.csv` containing information about all the files in the subset. This information can be divided into two groups:

- Metadata: Contains file name, the cutoff frequency and the resonance (in MIDI note and in Volts¹)
- Features: Contains information such as the estimated pitch, the input delay, and some other spectral features (RMS energy, MFCCs, ...)

Because the VCF has self oscillating capabilities, some of the signals have been “eaten” by the filter itself. In order to clarify this, all the estimated pitches are shown in Figure 11. Ideally, a smooth line around the fundamental frequency should be visible, but instead there are a few peaks with a higher predicted pitch.

It is observed that at higher values (95, 111, and 127), the pitch deviates from the expected values. This deviation is attributed to the filter itself, where the oscillation frequency is given by the value for the cutoff frequency. This phenomenon is further evidenced by examining the Root Mean Square (RMS) values (see Figure 12), which show a significant increase when self-oscillation occurs.

In addition to this, it can be seen that as the pitch goes higher, the values also change as the signal gets filtered out, but this only means that the signal doesn't have enough amplitude for the algorithm to accurately estimate the pitch. This explains why higher frequencies like B5 get more of the “unexpected” results (see Figure 13).

¹Values in Volts are estimations.

Figure 11: Pitch estimation for every note

Figure 12: RMS for every note

Another important aspect is the input delay. This delay was measured by comparing a reference MIDI note with the recorded sound. The results show a consistent delay of approximately 44 milliseconds, with a few exceptions (see Figure 14). These results are reasonable, considering the signal has to travel through the USB connection twice, accounting for roughly 20 milliseconds per trip.

Figure 13: B5 estimated pitch, Resonance and Cutoff values

Figure 14: Input delay measured for every note

4.1.2 Kobol_VCO_dynamic

The second subset of the dataset is made of 7680 audio files, divided in three folders, **dry**, **dry_trimmed**, and **wet**. The idea behind this subset is to collect for a few VCO notes, with different cutoff frequencies, resonance, VCO waveform, and different envelope attack and decay values applied to the VCF.

- **wet**: Contains the files generated by recording the “AUDIO OUT” output from the synthesizer.
- **dry**: Contains the files generated by recording the “VCO 1 OUT” output from the synthesizer
- **dry_trimmed**: Contains the same files as dry but cut to match the format of the signals from wet and with a 10 milliseconds fade-in and fade-out, in order to prevent clicks and pops by ensuring smooth transitions at the start and end of cut audio signals. The code used to create this signals can be found on GitHub².

The structure for the three folders is the same. Each folder contains 4 more folders for every MIDI note the VCO is playing. For every note, there are 640 files named:

`BX_Y.wav`

Where X ranges from 2 to 5, and Y ranges from 1 to 640. This naming style is different from the first subset, and the reason is because in the second subset there are 5 different variables, so in order to keep the names cleaner and easier to understand, a decision was made to use a simpler naming system.

Additionally, there are 4 CSV files. The first one is called `file_info.wav`, and it contains the metadata for all the files in the subset. It contains the file name, attack and decay values, the VCO waveform, the cutoff frequency and the resonance (last 3 in MIDI note and in Volts³). The other 3 CSV files called `audio_features_name of the folder.csv` contain the features for the files in the specified folder like pitch, input delay, etc...

For this subset, the MIDI values that make the VCF self oscillate have been removed, so a close inspection still shows a few unexpected set of values, that can be depicted in Figure 15.

²https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/Thesis_code

³Values in Volts are estimations.

Figure 15: Estimated pitch for every note

This values appear every time the waveform gets the 108 (or an estimated 8.5 Volts). For this specific waveform, the algorithm fails at predicting pitch in an accurate way. This is clearly seen if both graphs are overlapped on top of each other, as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Estimated pitch and Waveform overlapped

An analysis of the spectrogram shows that, as the MIDI value for the waveform increases, the harmonic content increases too. In the example from Figure 17 we

can see the same note, with the same parameters, and the 4 waveforms that were registered.

Figure 17: Spectrograms for different notes

In addition to this, another unexpected set of values every time the the synth hits this values:

- Waveform: 36
- Cutoff: 63
- Resonance: 79

The reason this occurs at these specific values is not clear, but it seems to be influenced by the decay values⁴. The decay parameter appears to play a significant role in determining the frequency at which these unusual values arise, suggesting a deeper connection between the decay setting and the resulting behavior of the system (see Figure 18).

In regards to the input delay, for this subset only the files in the `wet` folder have relevant results. The `dry` folder contains continuous signals, so no delay can be

⁴Attack and decay values were set manually, so the values recorded in the .csv file are for reference only.

Figure 18: Similarity between specific pitch peaks and Decay values

measured, and the files in `dry_trimmed` have been created manually, meaning that the input delay will be affected by how we configure the trimming script⁵. For these reasons, the input delay from the files in the `wet` folder was measured against a reference MIDI file, similarly to the first subset.

The results are similar to the ones in the first subset because the process to extract the data was very similar. Once again, results show a rather consistent delay of 44 milliseconds (see Figure 19).

⁵https://github.com/AlvaroCrespo02/Thesis_code

Figure 19: Input delay measured for every note

4.2 Model

4.2.1 Modulation Extraction for LFO-driven Audio Effects

After dealing with troubleshooting issues with the codebase, and with the experiments for the second model running in parallel, the time left to test the first model was very limited.

During the training phase of the model, significant thermal challenges were encountered due to the reliance on CPU-based computation rather than GPU acceleration. The intensive nature of the training process caused the laptop’s temperature to spike to high temperatures, raising concerns about the potential strain on the hardware and its longevity. Despite efforts to mitigate this issue by reducing the dataset size, lowering the sample rate, and adjusting various model parameters, the computational demands remained beyond the capabilities of the laptop’s CPU. This situation underscored the need for more robust hardware, such as a GPU, to efficiently handle the model’s training requirements without risking damage to the system.

Data extracted using HWiNFO⁶ confirmed the thermal issue. As shown in Figure 20, the laptop's temperature rises to critical levels as soon as the code starts running. This is unsustainable given that the console log reflects a training time of 23 minutes per epoch:

```
"Epoch 0: 0% | 0/125 [00:22<22:49, 0.09it/s, v_num=96,
train/loss_step=0.278]"
```

These values are for 100 audio files (70 for training, 30 for validation) with a sample rate of 32 kHz and a batch size of 12, among other configurations, making it relatively small compared to the original 2560 files in the subset. Even with this small amount of data, the model requires too much computational power to run properly.

Under these circumstances, further experiments cannot be performed without better hardware.

Figure 20: CPU temperature over time

⁶<https://www.hwinfo.com/about-software/>

4.2.2 Pedalnet

In contrast to the first model, pedalnet ran successfully and produced some results. It is important to note that, due to the nature of this model, not every training step has a recorded value. As a result, the training plots are presented as scatter plots rather than continuous lines.

After several attempts and training sessions, the obtained results are shown in Figure 21, using the following hyperparameters:

- batch_size: 64
- data: data_1note_noResOsc.pickle
- dilation_depth: 8
- kernel_size: 3
- learning_rate: 0.001
- num_channels: 16
- num_repeat: 3
- num_epochs: 100

Figure 21: Validation results over number of epochs

The validation metrics are relatively stable across epochs, with the validation loss hovering around 0.94 to 0.98, and the validation MAE and RMSE not showing significant improvement. This could suggest that the model is not generalizing well or that the validation set is consistently challenging. The validation RMSE remains quite high (around 2136), and there's no noticeable improvement or worsening trend, indicating that the model's performance on the validation set is stagnant.

Figure 22: Training results over number of steps

Data in Figure 22 shows that the training loss shows slight fluctuations but generally hovers around the 0.94 to 0.98 range. There's no significant decrease or clear trend indicating that the model is consistently improving or overfitting over time. Both the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) show significant variation across epochs. There are epochs where these values increase significantly, which could indicate that the model is encountering difficult training instances or that the learning rate might be causing instability.

After some experimentation, some new tests were made with updated hyperparameters:

- `batch_size`: 16
- `data`: `data_1note_noResOsc.pickle`
- `dilation_depth`: 8
- `kernel_size`: 3
- `learning_rate`: 0.0001

- num_channels: 32
- num_repeat: 2
- num_epochs: 100

Figure 23: Validation results over number of epochs

The validation loss, MAE, and RMSE shown in Figure 23 have become slightly more stable and lower in the new model compared to the old one, particularly towards the later epochs. The validation RMSE in the new model stabilizes around 2104–2106, which is a slight improvement over the previous model’s 2136 range.

Figure 24: Training results over number of epochs

The training loss in the new model is slightly more variable, with values ranging from around 0.91 to 1.00 towards the later epochs. This variability suggests that the model might be encountering different levels of difficulty across epochs. The training MAE and RMSE also show significant variability. In some epochs, the training MAE and RMSE are relatively low, but they spike significantly in others, indicating that the model's performance is inconsistent across different training data batches (see Figure 24).

The new model shows a modest improvement in validation metrics, which is a positive sign that the model might be generalizing better, but the training metrics are more variable, which could suggest it's encountering more complex patterns or perhaps instability during training.

Overall, while the validation performance has improved, the variability in training metrics may need further investigation to ensure the model is learning consistently. In both cases, the validation loss did not drop below 0.95, which is not the desired outcome. However, given that the original code underwent a significant overhaul, making it more complex, it is possible that the new version still requires further

improvement before achieving results similar to the original model.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 About the dataset

During the creation of the dataset, several significant challenges were encountered, particularly in dealing with analog equipment and the potential for human error.

Working with analog synthesizers presents unique difficulties due to their inherent instability and lack of precision. These devices require frequent tuning, are sensitive to environmental factors like temperature and humidity, and their parameters can be difficult to replicate precisely, given the limitations of modern potentiometers. Moreover, older equipment that has undergone little to no maintenance is often unreliable and prone to unexpected failures.

Human error, on the other hand, is an unpredictable yet time-consuming factor. It's easy to overlook small details, forget to press the record button, or accidentally delete important files. Such mistakes can be particularly costly when creating a dataset, as even a minor error can ruin a substantial portion of a recording session, significantly extending the project timeline. This underscores the importance of designing a recording system that allows for efficient data collection, minimizing the likelihood of errors and saving valuable time.

Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring the integrity of the dataset, which

in turn impacts the overall quality and reliability of the subsequent analysis and modeling.

That being said, the results for the dataset are quite satisfactory. Despite the challenges, the dataset achieved a good balance, offering a variety of results while maintaining a high level of consistency.

5.2 About the models

The modeling part of the thesis highlights a significant challenge associated with black-box modeling: the substantial computational power required to train state-of-the-art models, which remains a barrier for many users. These models are typically optimized for GPU execution, and attempting to run them on CPU is not only time-consuming but also risks significantly reducing the lifespan of the hardware. This limitation highlights an accessibility issue, where the lack of adequate computational power hinders broader experimentation and application by users.

Additionally, it highlights the often-overlooked aspect of research that involves significant troubleshooting and problem-solving, which is critical yet rarely discussed in academic literature. Acknowledging these challenges provides a more comprehensive view of the research process and contributes to the transparency and reproducibility of the study.

For future work, two primary directions could be pursued. The first involves utilizing more advanced hardware to run these models on the entire dataset, or at least a larger portion of it. This approach could yield more robust results but would still be dependent on access to high-performance computing resources. Alternatively, another line of work could be trying to make this models smaller and more efficient in terms of computational power. This direction is particularly interesting, since it would grant access for more users to run this models, enabling for more contributions to research.

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Appendix A

MCV24 Instructions

Since the use of the Doepfer MCV24 is not trivial, a small set of instructions were written for future use of the device with the RSF Expander Kobol. It is important to notice that output 1 (used in this example) has a 12-bit DAC optimised for $-2 \sim 8V$ at one volt per octave scaling. The RSF Expander Kobol has a $0 \sim 10V$ range, so it is recommended to use outputs 5 to 24.

Instructions to Operate the Device from Scratch (Basic)

To initiate sound production from scratch, follow these basic instructions:

1. Connect a cable from the device to the MIDI input. Ensure to verify the MIDI channel through which the information is being sent.
2. Simultaneously press the three buttons on the MCV, then release them. This step is recommended only if the user is completely lost, as it effectively resets the device and the “workbuffer”. This action also addresses the issue of the MCV24 screen displaying "Warmboot MCV24". After pressing the buttons, the screen should show “Coldboot MCV24” along with a few other messages, indicating that the device is ready for use.

3. The device features a “main” menu and several sub-menus. The main menu appears as depicted in the figure below. If this menu is not visible, press the menu button to display it. Primarily, sub-menu B or “CV Parameter” will be used. Once this menu is located, there is no need to exit it unless otherwise instructed.

Figure 25: Menu "A" from the MCV24

4. For this example, output 1 will be used as the CV information output, and output 13 as the trigger output.
 - (a) Select output 01 using the output wheel, and turn the menu wheel until “Midito” is found. Adjust the value wheel until “NoteEvent” is displayed, then press the value button.

Figure 26: Selecting "NoteEvent"

- (b) Continue turning the menu wheel until “Midichannel” is found, then select the desired MIDI channel for information retrieval.

Figure 27: Selecting the MIDI channel

- (c) Proceed by turning the menu wheel until “Trigger” (located on the upper row) is found, and change the value to “Direct”. Turn the menu wheel once more, and select Output 13 as an output.

Figure 28: Trigger mode

Figure 29: Trigger channel

At this stage, the basic configuration is complete. If a cable is connected from output

13 to the “GATE IN” of the Kobol, the Gate LED should illuminate each time a MIDI note is sent from the device. To modify the pitch, connect a cable from output 1 of the MCV24 to “CV IN 1V/oct”. Note that the synthesizer may be out of tune at this point.

Warning: Since this is a basic setup, the synthesizer might produce high-frequency sounds. To prevent this, it is recommended to turn the FREQUENCY knob all the way down (and generally avoid increasing it), then close the filter, and finally connect the cable. Alternatively, keep the output volume of the synthesizer at a minimum and gradually increase it.

Additional Configuration

The following configurations have been tested and seem to enhance performance, although the underlying reasons are not fully understood.

Tuning the Kobol with the MCV24 (Using C3 as Reference)

1. Change the BaseNote from the CV output to G3.
2. Adjust the TUNE knob of the synthesizer to achieve a C3 note. This adjustment can result in a satisfactory sound, although other octaves may sound flat.

Figure 30: Changing the base note

Appendix B

RSF Expander Kobol

The original instruction manual for the synthesiser were written in french, so they had to be translated.

Expander I-KOBOL

19, rue Claire CAZELLES 31200-TOULOUSE Tel. (61) 47.31.62 R.C.: Tise 79 B
269 SIRET: 315 734 954.000 11

DESCRIPTION:

The EXPANDER KOBOL is a complete synthesizer that can be used in a standalone manner. Its design and standard 4-unit rack presentation make it a universal module. The EXPANDER KOBOL can be used controlled by a monophonic or polyphonic synthesizer to expand its capabilities, as well as a sound source when connected to an analog sequencer or any control system (joystick, microcomputer, etc.).

Several Expanders (from 2 to 8 channels) mounted in a rack can form the basis of a modular polyphonic system. An internal selection allows adaptation of the EXPANDER's trigger input (GATE) to all existing standards.

The EXPANDER KOBOL innovates compared to all current systems by generalizing the "VOLTAGE CONTROL" principle: all its functions are voltage-controllable.

On a conventional synthesizer, only the VCO, VCF, VCA are voltage-controlled, the EXPANDER has 16 parameters with this capability, thus opening up new possibilities for musicians. Any parameter can be controlled in real-time by an LFO, an envelope, a pedal, the analog output of a microcomputer, or stored in memory by an external programmer.

The EXPANDER KOBOL is the basic element of the RSF modular synthesizer range. It can be coupled with the PROGRAMMER module, which stores 16 sounds chosen by the musician. It can also be complemented by the EXPANDER II, which includes all the necessary additional functions for creating an extremely powerful modular system.

The EXPANDER KOBOL is a complete synthesizer. It is equipped with two "VCO" oscillators, a low-frequency oscillator "LFO", a 24 dB/octave low-pass filter "VCF", three voltage-controlled amplifiers "VCA", two envelopes with three parameters "ADS", an amplifier, adder, inverter "VOLTAGE PROCESSOR". All these functions are pre-connected to each other for use according to the conventional configuration. The input/output of each function is available on the front panel, allowing disconnection of the internal pre-wiring and the realization of the desired connection by the user.

Designed and manufactured by RSF, the creator of the KOBOL synthesizer range, the EXPANDER is the basic module of a vast modular synthesizer program.

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS:

VCO 1 and VCO 2:

- Voltage-controlled oscillators 1 V/octave.
- Frequency range: 0.1 Hz to 100 KHz.
- Temperature coefficient: 50 ppm.
- Synchronization of VCO 2 relative to VCO 1.

- Waveforms: triangle, ramp, doubled ramp, square, variable-width pulses, pulses controlled by ADS 2 envelope, progressive mixing between these waveforms controlled by voltage.
- Tuning adjustment for both VCOs.
- Independent VCA for each VCO.

VCF:

- Voltage-controlled filter 1 V/octave.
- Frequency range: 5 Hz to 100 KHz.
- 24 dB/octave slope.
- Resonance adjustment with end-of-travel oscillation.
- Keyboard control adjustment from 0 V/octave to 2 V/octave.
- Amplitude adjustment by ADS 2 control.

ADS 1 and ADS 2:

- Attack, Decay, Sustain envelope type.
- Decay suppression for ADS 1 envelope.
- Time control range: 1 ms to 100s.
- Output amplitude: 0 to 10 V.
- GATE input: trigger on the rising or falling edge (by internal selection).
- Trigger threshold: 2 V.

NOISE GENERATOR:

- Random digital noise generator, white or pink by internal selection.

LFO:

- Voltage-controlled low-frequency oscillator.
- Frequency range: 0.001 Hz to 100 Hz.
- Triangular or square signal outputs.

VOLTAGE PROCESSOR:

- Adder, amplifier, inverter.
- IN1: variable gain input from 0 to 2, +10 volts pre-connected to this input.
- IN2: gain 2 input.
- Normal and inverted output of the signals present at the input.

VOLTAGE CONTROL:

- Sixteen parameters are voltage-controllable.
- Control voltage range for potentiometer centered: -4 V to +4 V.
- Connector for flat cable for storing the 16 parameters by the PROGRAMMER module. In this case, the front panel buttons remain active as well as the control inputs by jacks.

OUTPUTS:

- VCO 1, VCO 2 with disconnection of the link to VCF.
- LFO before and after VOLUME potentiometer.
- ADS 1 and ADS 2.

CONNECTIONS:

- 6.35 mm Jacks.

EQUIPMENT:

- 33 integrated circuits.

WEIGHT:

- 3 kg.

DIMENSIONS:

- 488 mm x 178 mm x 130 mm.

POWER CONSUMPTION:

- 5 VA.
- 200/240 V AC.